

FINANCIAL LITERACY: A KEY TO FINANCIAL INCLUSION. A STUDY CONDUCTED FOR TIER I AND TIER II CITIES

Abstract: *India is a developing nation, and most surveys show that financial literacy in India is very poor. Two-third of the people lack financial planning basics, which means that they are financially illiterate. One of the reasons for crisis in personal finance can be low literacy level in finance. It is found that 77% of the adults present all over the world are considered financial illiterates. This amounts to the lack of comprehending concepts (financial) by approximately 4 billion people all over the world. As financial-literacy has a direct bearing on the economic growth of a country, therefore it has become an important for the educators of worldwide. Financial literacy is important for people for right financial choices.*

In the current research paper, an attempt is made to understand and identify the numerous aspects which are important in defining and measuring financial-literacy in Indian context. An index for measuring financial literacy has been arrived at and proposed for college going students. A comparison of financial literacy has been drawn among tier I and tier II cities of India. It was found that behavior, knowledge & attitude related to finance along with demographics and socio-economic factors has a major impact on the level of financial knowledge of the student.

Keywords: *Financial-literacy, Financial inclusion, Tier I and tier II cities, college students, socio-economic factors, literacy level*

JEL Classification: *B26, F65, G4, G53, G32, G2, G21, G51, G53*

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I.Introduction

Knowledge about finance is referred to as financial literacy. Many financial-literacy definitions are in vogue and all of them state that they are the abilities of individuals to collect and evaluate information that are needed for sound decisions financially that help them in future. When any person correctly answers atleast three out of four financial concepts, he or she is defined as financially literate. It is found that 77% of the adults present all over the world are considered financial illiterates. This amounts to the lack of comprehending concepts (financial) by approximately 4 billion people all over the world (**Klapper, L., & Van Oudheusden, P.,2015**)

Surveys conducted in India shows that financial literacy in still poor in India. Over two-third of the population lack financial basics, i.e., they are not financial literate. In a survey conducted by Standard and Poor from 2014, it was found that only 24% Indian adults could understand basics of financial planning (**Aegonlife, 2018**). Meeting our financial goals and bringing prosperity in our life is the key to our financial plan. When an individual is able to manage his income well enough to meet his needs and dreams as well as create wealth for a comfortable cushion for any emergency, it is called a sound financial planning (Agarwal, T. (2016)).

With all these taken into consideration, the need for enhancing financial literacy becomes an important agenda as it had direct bearing on the economic condition of any given country. It is alarming to know that India is way behind other countries in financial literacy. In a survey done globally, it was found that Indian financial-illiterate adults' amount to 20% world's financial-illiterate population, and close to 25% of the adults in India understand basic concepts of personal finance.

GAPS IN LEARNING

A Standard and Poor's survey found that three-fourth of Indians are not financially literate. Here are some more findings from the survey.

% of adults answering correctly

Topic	India	BRICS	South Asia*	World
Risk diversification	14	28	18	35
Inflation	56	46	46	50
Interest	48	48	46	49
Compound interest	44	44	39	45
Financially literate %	24	28	23	33

*excluding India

There is a wide variation in financial literacy around the world (% of adults)

Women trail men in financial literacy (% of adults)

Financial literacy lowest among adults age 65+ (% of adults)

Source: LiveMint, Dec 16, 2015

II. Significance in India

Like in other developed nations, financial literacy has still not become a priority in India. When there is shortcome of basic financial literacy, it results in poor financial decisions and investments. And that is the reason, why we observe that most of the people invest in physical assets and short-term plans to accomplish their personal goals. This results in getting lesser benefits and also does not contribute anything in the economic development of the country. India has an ambition of becoming an economic superpower, but the poor financial-literacy rate can prove to be a major hindrance in achieving this ambition, and therefore the developing country like India needs to realize the importance of financial-literacy.

III. Financial-literacy: Key to Financial-Inclusion

PMJDY(Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana) is the premier inclusion program in finance in our country. Universal access to bank account has been made a near reality by this programme but it has been observed that the usage level of these accounts remains very low. There are 180 billion accounts in India, but according to the World-Bank's Global-Findex-Database, there has been no transaction in almost 48 percent of these accounts. It must be remembered that regular usage and not access is the right measure of financial inclusion. Financial-literacy is a skill where people need to be literate enough to understand the basics of managing money.

IV. Review of Literature:

Research conducted by experts has revealed that a positive relationship exists between financial education and its effect on financial market developments as well as demographic and economic

changes in our country. Central bank, Reserve-Bank-of-India is actively seen participation in eradicating the financial illiteracy in India. "Project financial-literacy" is the project which has been implemented by the bank in this context. The results of a survey which was conducted by Financial express says that rapid progress is made by India has resulted it being ranked among the top ten nations of the world, in the field of financial education (**Nash 2012**). Serious worries about the capability of people to secure financial well-being is reported from the research from around the world.

Evidences are available that individuals are often indebted because of their failure to understand the nuances of wise investment and the illeffect of under saving (**Mitchell 2011; Poterba, 2007**). Across the nations, this kind of behaviour is more predominant among the younger people. In their latest report on student indebtedness in the US, Reed and Cochrane observe that 75% of the students were embroiled in debt due to credit card borrowings and education loans (**Reed and Cochrane, 2012**). There are evidence from around the world which shows that deficiency in financial-literacy is widespread.

These studies have led to development and implementation of various financial education programs for all groups of individuals all over the world. Though these programs which are launched have a very wide scope and reach all sections of societies. The main objective behind these programs are to improve financial behavior, attitude and knowledge of the individuals which will empower them and to make intelligent choices that will have a positive bearing on their finances (**Xu & Zia, 2012**). Financial literacy among young in the US has been investigated by collecting data through recent research. Through questionnaire, the various aspects of the readiness of the youth in making good decisions financially and factors determining the literacy level in youth & its improvement was sought. The youth were found to be possessing low level of knowledge in finance. (**Lusardi et al., 2010**). This inference was found to be consistent with the findings across the world. It was found that socio-economic condition and financial situation of the family had significantly influenced the level of financial literacy among youths. Significant differences were also found among men and women, and women were found to be possessing low level of knowledge in money matters. The results were repeated by **Agnew & Szykman (2005)**, **Mitchell & Lusardi (2008)**, and similar studies conducted elsewhere by **Rooij, V. et al. (2007)**, **Mitchel (2007)** & **Smith and Stewart (2009)**.

It was found the respondents with college degree scored better in awareness related to money matters. Family also played as a great influencer. The use of financial knowledge was also to be one of important factors: **Hudson (2010)**.

Danes&Hira (1987) concluded that females had a better sense of overall financial management and males had more knowledge about subjects like insurance and loans especially personal loans.

Very little research is conducted on how the various factors like income, family background affected the level of awareness related to money matters: **Alcon (1999)**.

V. Methodology:

Review of literature has revealed that there has been more focus on the knowledge component of financial literacy (Heenkenda, S. (2014)). But ultimately what influences financial-literacy is the financial-behavior along with attitude and knowledge. The purpose of the current research is to identify literacy level in finance level by considering the knowledge, attitude and behaviour along with demographic and socio-economic characteristics of post graduate students. The current research undertaken concentrates on 3 aspects of literacy level in finance, i.e. attitude, behavior & knowledge. Therefore, questions representing all the three aspects are included here. To identify the literacy level in finance, questions have been classified as easy, medium and difficult (**Volpe, 2002**) (**Table I**).

Depending on level of difficulty, different weightages have been given to questions. Questions on financial behavior, knowledge and attitude have been included in the questionnaire. Different weightage has been given to questions, based on their difficulty-level. Thirty questions (Annexure) based on financial knowledge aspect have been included and marks (*1-easy, 1.5-medium and 2-difficult*) have been allocated.

Table I: *Clasification of questions related to knowledge as per the level of difficulty

Level	Easy	Medium	Difficult
Question Number	6,7,14,15,16,19,22,23, 24, 26,30,32,33,34,35	8,10,11,12,21,2 5,28,37,40	9,13,17,20,27,29 31,36,38,39
Total no. of questions	15	10	10
Weight assigned	1	1.5	2
Marks	15	15	20

*Self Computed

Table II: *Category (area) Wise Marks to Questions

Area (question number)	Marks
Knowledge (6-35)	50
Attitude (36-40)	25
Behavior (41-45)	25

*Self Computed

Since the respondents of the questionnaire are students, more weightage is allocated to knowledge component. In India, parents support their wards financially. So they do not have well developed behavior & attitude towards financial matters. There are four areas where the questionnaire

concentrates on, namely Savings and Borrowings, General personal finance knowledge, Insurance and Investment. Areas like insurance, banking and retirement planning and securities are included under national strategy on financial education and hence have been included in this research.

To explore the literacy level in finance of the post graduate students, exploratory and descriptive research design has been used in the present study and then the effect of their socio-economic demographics and on literacy level in finance are described. Non-probability convenient sampling technique was chosen. The total sample size is 76 comprising of post-graduate students.

Ho: There is no significant association among students' financial knowledge, attitude, behaviour and demographics & socio-economic variables and their literacy level in finance.

For measuring financial-literacy, students cumulative score which were the % of right answers was calculated-Lyons, 2007, out of 35 questions. Mean and median % was calculated for the right answers. On an average (Mean), the results showed that 38.90 questions were answered correctly by students. The median %age of correct scores is **38.5**. Students were classified into subgroups based on the % of right answers taken from median. Students with scores equal/above median ($38.5 = 39$) are clasified as students who **passed** the test and thus are considered to have higher financial-litracy level and students with scores below median ($38.5 = 39$) are clasified as students who **failed** the test and thus are considered to have lower financial-litreacy level.

Out of 76 student respondents, 46.05% students scored above the median and thus passed the test and 53.94% of students have scored lower than median and effectively failed the test.

Binomial logistic regression was used to determine the effect of independent variables on dependent variables.

To check the hypothesis, the independent variables were students' knowledge, behaviour & attitude along with demographics and variables such as, students age, gender, which city the sudent hails from, family annual income, period of work experience, and whether the student is a domicile of Karnataka. The dependent variable is literacy level in finance.

The various parameters of model:

1. Chi-Square,
2. Omnibus-tests of model-coefficients,
3. Cox&Snell R^2
4. Negelkerke R^2
5. Wald statistics, Exp(B)

Table III: *Coding of the variables.

Study Variables: Dependent and Independent Variables for Logistic Regression

Dependent Variables (DV) - Financial Literacy	Categorical Variable - 0 if respondent possesses lower level of financial literacy 1 if respondent possesses higher level of financial literacy
Covariates	
Financial Knowledge Index	This is cumulative score of General Personal financial Knowledge score, Savings and borrowings Knowledge score and Insurance Knowledge score. It is an additive indicator.
Financial Attitude Index	It is an additive indicator
Financial Behaviour Index	It is an additive indicator
Independent Variable (IV)	
Gender	Dichotomous Variable - 0 if respondent is a Female 1 if respondent is a Male
Age	Multinomial variable with value of 1 for 21-23 years 2 for 24-26 years 3 for 27 years and above
Family Annual Income	Multinomial variable with value of 0 for No income 1 for 0-99999 2 for 1,00,000-4,99,999 3 for 5,00,000-9,99,999 5 for 10,00,000 and above
Work experience in months	Multinomial variable
City which the student belongs to	Dichotomous Variable - 0 for Tier 2 cities 1 for Tier 1 cities
Domicile of Karnataka	Dichotomous Variable - 0 for No 1 for Yes

* Self Computed Table

Table IV depicts that the prediction capability of literacy level in finance was 53.9% without the model

Table IV: *Classification Table

		Predicted			
		CUMULATIVE FINANCIAL LITERACY SCORE		Percentage Correct	
Observed		F	P		
Step 0	CUMULATIVE FINANCIAL LITERACY SCORE	F	41	0	100.0
		P	35	0	.0
Overall Percentage					53.9

a. Constant is included in the model.

b. The cut value is .500

* Self Computed Table

The final model developed by the researcher taking into consideration all the independent variables and its effect on the level of literacy in finance among post graduate student was used to measure the impact of each variable (independent) using various statistical tests.

1.1 Model-Chi-square

This test was used to find out whether our model that includes our full set of predictors is a significant improvement over the null model. To check the overall fit of the model, 2 hypotheses were developed

H0: The predictors do not have significant effect.

Table V: *Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients

	Chi-square	df	Sig.
Step 1 Step	104.884	23	.000**
Block	104.884	23	.000
Model	104.884	23	.000

* Self Computed Table

**($p < 0.05$)

From Table V, the model has 23 df(degrees-of-freedom) exhibiting a 104.884 with 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) ($\chi^2(23) = 104.884, (p < .01)$).

Hence, the null hypotheses is rejected and it is concluded that predictors do have a significant effect on the prediction. So, researchers can do further analysis to determine how the independent variables are the significant in prediction of financial-literacy levels.

1.2 Model Summary: Likelihood Ratio Test (-2LL ratio):

Table VI: *Model Summary

	-2 Log likelihood	Cox & Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square
1	.000**	.748	1.000

* Self Computed Table

**Estimation terminated at iteration number 20 because maximum iterations has been reached. Final solution cannot be found. ($p < 0.05$)

The significance level was found to be less than 0.05 and thus was concluded that there is a evidence statistically that the dependent variable has significant relationship with the various combinations of independent variables.

Cox&Snell ‘s R^2 is a different version of Multiple- R^2 . Table VI, indicates a major portion that is 74.8% of behaviour of deperendent variable can be attributed through this model. A very strong Nagelkerke ‘s R^2 value was (1.000), indicating a strong relationship of 100% between the predictors and the level of literacy in financial matters of post graudate students can be explained by the various combinations of independent variables.

1.3 Hosmer- Lemeshow Test

This test helped the researchers to further classify the subjects into 7 groups which was based on their literacy level related to financial matters and thus re-emphasising that the model prediction are accurate statistically.

Table VII: * Hosmer and Lemeshow Test

Step	Chi-square	df	Sig. (if p>0.05)
1	.000	7	1.000

*Self Computed Table

Table VIII depicts that the independent variables have influence on the dependent variable and thus the null hypothesis is to be rejected.

Table VIII: *Contingency Table for Hosmer and Lemeshow Test

	CUMULATIVE FINANCIAL LITERACY SCORE = F		CUMULATIVE FINANCIAL LITERACY SCORE = P		Total
	Observed	Expected	Observed	Expected	
Step 1 1	8	8.000	0	.000	8
2	8	8.000	0	.000	8
3	8	8.000	0	.000	8
4	8	8.000	0	.000	8
5	8	8.000	0	.000	8
6	1	1.000	7	7.000	8
7	0	.000	8	8.000	8
8	0	.000	2	2.000	2
9	0	.000	18	18.000	18

*Self Computed Table

From Table VIII, based on the estimated probabilities, the nine ordered-groups are formed. The groups probabilities lower than 0.1 form the first group and grouping is continued till the probability of 1.0 is arrived at. The groups are further divided into actual observed outcome variables that is Pass or Fail. With the goodness-of-fit being more than 0.05, the researchers succeeded to reject null hypothesis and arrive at a result that the model estimates fit the data at an acceptable level and predictions obtained from the model does not significantly differ from the observed outcomes.

1.4 Model fit

The model fit from table IX showed that classification of the respondents was perfect and that all the respondents were classified correctly. It also shows that

- 76 cases predicted to be under low level of literacy in finance group,
- Out of which 41 cases were observed to be in very low level of literacy in finance group,
- None of the 76 were wrongly classified under High level of literacy in finance group
- Similarly, 35 cases predicted to be high level of literacy in finance group,
- And all 35 were correctly classified as high level of literacy in finance,
- none of the 35 cases are under low level of literacy in finance group.

So, out of total 76 cases, all were correctly classified making the model prediction as 100%.

Table IX: *Classification Table**

Observed			Predicted		
			CUMULATIVE FINANCIAL LITERACY SCORE		Percentage Correct
			F	P	
Step 1	CUMULATIVE FINANCIAL LITERACY SCORE	F	41	0	100.0
		P	0	35	100.0
Overall Percentage					100.0

*Self Computed Table

**The cut value is .500

This depicted that the research could use the model for predicting the level of literacy in finance among post graduate students with absolute accuracy which without the model was only 53.9% accurate.

2. Conclusion

Behavior, knowledge & attitude related to finance along with demographics and socio-economic factors such as, students' age, gender, which city the student hails from, family annual income, period of work experience and whether the student is a

domicile of Karnataka has a major impact on the level of financial knowledge of the student. The awareness related to money matters among students is taken as dependent variable. This study was able to identify and prove that the researchers could predict the financial-literacy level with 100% accuracy with the current model.

The current research has many limitations. Non-probability convenience sample method is used to collect data. The information is collected from cities. If the same study is conducted in rural areas, then the result may vary. Thirdly, post graduate students are only considered for data collection and other sections of the society are ignored.

3. Scope for further Research

Focus of the present research is to identify level of awareness in finance related matters, financial-literacy level by considering the Knowledge, Attitude and Behaviour along with demographic and socio-economic characteristics of post graduate students. Researchers can expand the study by considering other sections of the society. Rural India can also be considered for further study.

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ANNEXURE:

GENERAL PERSONAL FINANCIAL KNOWLEDGE SCORE

1. A person's aggregate deposits in a bank, including fixed deposits, are insured up to 1 lakh by
2. If you invest Rs. 20000 today at 4% for a year, your balance in a year will be
3. Which of the following investments requires that you keep your money invested for a specified period or face an early withdrawal penalty
4. Which of the following statements is TRUE about the annual percentage rate (APR)?
5. You can receive your credit report from
6. Which is FALSE concerning credit cards?
7. An overdraft
8. You will improve your creditworthiness by
9. If you co-sign a loan for a friend, then

SAVINGS AND BORROWINGS

10. Auto Insurance companies determine your premium based on
11. The main reason to purchase insurance is to
12. The main reason to purchase insurance is to
13. _____ would not ordinarily be covered under a homeowners policy.
14. Which of the following statements is FALSE?
15. You have a better chance of resolving a complaint against an insurance company by bringing the issue to a government agency at the

INSURANCE

16. If interest rates rise, the price of a treasury bond will
17. A rupee cost averaged approach to investing involves
18. A high-risk and high return investment strategy would be most suitable for
19. Which of the following is FALSE?
20. The returns from a balanced mutual fund include
21. No-load mutual funds are recommended over load funds because investors
22. If other factors remain the same, the US dollars value of Indian fund will be

INVESTMENTS/ATTITUDE

23. Assume you're in your early twenties and you would like to build up your nest egg for a secure retirement in 30 years. Which of the following approaches would best meet your needs?
24. Assuming you are in your early twenties without any dependents, which of the following would you do regarding your life insurance?
25. You have just graduated from college and found a job earning Rs 6,00,000 per year. You will pay Rs 10,000 per month for five years for student loans. You have a monthly balance on each of your three credit cards. What should you do to improve your financial health?
26. Do you maintain financial records?
27. Using the scale given below please rank the importance of items numbered [Maintaining adequate financial records]
28. Using the scale given below please rank the importance of items numbered [Spending less than your income]
29. Using the scale given below please rank the importance of items numbered [Maintaining adequate insurance coverage]
30. Using the scale given below please rank the importance of items numbered [Planning and implementing a regular investment program]

